

GENERAL CULTURE IN EDUCATORS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION ORGANIZATION DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETENCE

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information about the competence of educators of the future preschool educational organization, the formation of the competence of social development of students, and the requirements for the pedagogical activity of educator-pedagogues.

Key words: Future preschool teacher, competence, education, training, cognitive,

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье представлены сведения о компетентности педагогов будущей дошкольной образовательной организации, формировании компетенции социального развития обучающихся, требованиях, предъявляемых к педагогической деятельности воспитателей-педагогов.

Ключевые слова: Будущий педагог дошкольного образования, компетентность, образование, обучение, познавательный,

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti tarbiyachilarining kompetensiya haqida, talabalarning ijtimoiy rivojlanish kompetensiyasini shakllantirishi, tarbiyachi-pedagoglarning pedagogik faoliyatiga qo'yilgan talablar haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyachisi, kompetensiya, ta'lim, tarbiya, kognitivlik,

Preschool education is one of the problems that is becoming one of the topical issues of the head of our country and state policy. The most important issue is to increase the creativity of preschool teachers and train them as qualified and potential

personnel. Giving knowledge to students is the teacher's responsible duty, Ibn Sina expressed the following thoughts about what a teacher's personality should be:

- to be strict and serious in dealing with children;
- to pay attention to how students acquire the given knowledge;
- use of different methods and forms in education;
- the student's memory, ability to acquire knowledge, knowledge of personal characteristics;
- to be interested in science;
- distinguish the most important of the given knowledge;
- providing knowledge in accordance with the age and intellectual level of students;
- it is necessary to achieve that each word is at the level of arousing children's emotions.

Science, literature and art, enlightenment progressed rapidly during the reign of Muhammad Taragai Mirza Ulugbek. Also, ideas such as class systems of teaching, teaching children by age, setting a specific period of educational work were put forward and implemented to a certain extent. At the same time, Ulugbek attached great importance to the knowledge and skills of teachers and teachers. He honored the most skilled teachers who ensured that their material needs were met from the state support. At the same time, he demanded that the mudarris participate in scientific research in addition to teaching.

Western pedagogues also expressed similar thoughts. For example, Disterverg: "A good teacher never deviates from his principles of education. A teacher should always work independently on himself, a bad teacher keeps telling the truth, and a good teacher teaches children to find the truth.

A preschool educator should have the following social and professional competencies that enable children's cognitive development:

1. Social competencies include the exchange of information between individuals, the expression of their interests and needs, the manifestation of tolerance towards other people and their opinions, the ability to work in a team and various support for other people with emotional stability includes the ability to give;
2. Cognitive competences are manifested in independent processing and structure of information, in search of new sources of information, concentration in studying or work, ability to use acquired knowledge and skills. different situations;
3. Operational competences - setting goals and work order, the ability to resist ambiguity and uncertainty, the ability to make and implement decisions, summarize work results, determine the work schedule;

4. Specific competencies include problem solving, self-management, being active in professional activities, adapting to new situations, evaluating and correcting plans, identifying errors and planning adequate ways to eliminate them. Therefore, professional competencies are the basis for the introduction of a competency approach to the pedagogical process and help the preschool teacher to acquire knowledge, skills and abilities in the implementation of innovative activities and the practical use of modern educational technologies. Preschool educator is one of the popular modern pedagogical professions. Educators should have the following: benevolent, sincere, friendly, polite, have a sense of humor, be patient, build relationships with children, prevent and resolve conflicts, self- He should supplement his knowledge by educating himself, know the method of preschool education and education.

To perform the activities effectively, a person should be attentive, responsible, sensitive, patient, show a tendency to work with children. The educator must have constant and great attention. Also, the educator should have the characteristic of mental activity: verbal-logical memory, the characteristic of activity goals: involuntary memory, according to the storage period of the material: short-term memory.

Communication qualities;

We need general culture and knowledge, competent and understandable speech, well-prepared voice, ability to manage a team, high communication skills.

Emotional and volitional qualities;

Resistance to stress, the ability to control one's behavior and emotions, and a strong nervous system are necessary: the work of a caregiver continues in conditions of constant psycho-emotional stress, even if it does not increase with physical effort.

The general cultural and national competencies of the educator of the future preschool education organization - loyalty to the motherland, kindness to people and belief in universal and national values, artistic and artistic works it is seen in the formation of abilities to understand, dress modestly, follow cultural rules and a healthy lifestyle. The educational potential of educators with universal competence is necessary for inculcating Uzbek national values in the minds of the young generation.

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